

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most typical is the American black bear, adopted by the brown bear and then the polar bear. Discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Could be darkish or light brown (cinnamon), sometimes even white. Not always black in coloration. 900,000 and never threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear might be discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nonetheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected underneath the U.S. □□ Measurement: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six feet in size. □□ Options: Most black bears are black, but their fur can vary from darkish brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on rare events. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are a few of the best at climbing trees. Their relatively smaller dimension and shorter claws make them fast and nimble to climb timber for protection, meals, and even hibernation. Nearly all of their weight loss plan is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Weight-reduction plan: Their different diet offers them the ability to live in a big vary of habitats. Additionally they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Dangerous? They're the most definitely bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And sure, they love honey.

The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Brown bears are probably the most widespread of all bear species, found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are accountable for almost all bear attacks in North America, with forty six per 12 months. Though their conservation standing is "least concern", their spread-out nature and decreased habitat make many of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide number of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large build, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the information, which led to the title of essentially the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and some even hunt young mammals comparable to elk and moose. Their shade varies from gentle blonde to dark brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are found in the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Size: Adults weigh 400 to 790 pounds, are 6.5 feet long, and have a shoulder top of 3.3 feet. □□ Weight loss program: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been known to prey on giant mammals. Coastal grizzlies are typically larger than those discovered within the Rocky Mountains on account of a richer eating regimen. Annually there are forty six assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Harmful? Recognized for his or her aggressive behavior, grizzlies are chargeable for essentially the most bear attacks in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are almost as giant as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, 8 feet long, and 4 feet tall on the shoulder. □□ Food plan: Their weight loss program is just like mainland grizzly bears. Nevertheless, attributable to extra plentiful food sources, the islands can assist a denser bear inhabitants. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to turn into their own subspecies. This has led to a more complicated social construction which leads to much less conflict between bears. □□ Harmful? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears might be aggressive. Attributable to their isolation, there is just one attack on humans every different year. Largest species of bear in the world weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Weight loss program is generally made up of meat, typically from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the biggest bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur seems white however is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears range in the snow-lined arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Dimension: Adult polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and may be 7 to 10 ft tall. They're a threatened species because of lack of habitat from climate change. Regardless of their huge measurement polar bears can be quick, sustaining a 6 mph tempo in the water. □□ Options: Compared to different bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, slender head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps won Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph pace! □□ Weight loss plan: Their weight loss plan consists principally of animals, especially seals which they will odor from a mile away. Though they appear white, their fur is actually clear and their skin is black. □□ Harmful? Polar bears might be extremely dangerous. They see humans as potential prey. Assaults are uncommon because of the distant nature of their habitat. Recognized for its cream colour chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Simple to tame and sometimes frequent in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is present in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The population is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is considered vulnerable. □□ Measurement: One of many smaller species, adults weigh around 300 pounds and stand forty seven to seventy five inches tall. □□ Weight loss program: Depending on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries,

seeds, insects, and honey. Attacks on humans are increasing as folks encroach on their habitat. ☐☐ Dangerous? They are certainly one of the easiest bears to tame (and due to this fact common in circuses), however Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found solely in China. 99% of its weight loss plan is bamboo. In fact, the second particular person in history to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas defending his sheep. Identified for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped body. ☐☐ Location: Pandas are found solely in China. Only 1,500 to 2,000 remain within the wild and they are considered a vulnerable species. ☐☐ Dimension: Pandas weigh around 300 pounds and may be over four ft tall, a powerful feat considering they weigh solely about 3.5 ounces at beginning. It additionally has a detailed cousin, the Qinling panda which has the same pattern in gentle brown and white. ☐☐ Food plan: Unlike different bears the panda's weight-reduction plan is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. ☐☐ Features: The giant panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped physique. All that fibrous bamboo retains them regular: they poop over forty instances a day! ☐☐ Dangerous? Attacks are uncommon but harmful, given that pandas have one in all the highest chunk forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing 55 to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. Eight to 10-inch long tongue for slurping up insects and honey. ☐☐ Location: The Solar bear is found within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It is the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is uncertain but considered weak and on the decline because of loss of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for their gallbladders and different body parts utilized in conventional medicines. ☐☐ Measurement: They stand solely 39 to fifty five inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. ☐☐ Options: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They're named for their pale, horseshoe-formed chest patch that looks like a rising sun. They also eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. ☐☐ Weight-reduction plan: Solar bears tear apart bushes and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." The truth is, they have an extremely long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. ☐☐ Dangerous? As a consequence of its shy nature, attacks are uncommon. Long, shaggy fur and mane gave them the identify sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. ☐☐ Location: The Sloth bear is found in the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining population of less than 20,000, they're considered vulnerable. ☐☐ Dimension: They're fifty five to 75 inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. ☐☐ Options: With their lengthy shaggy fur and mane, they're straightforward to inform aside from different Asiatic bears. In reality, they are very quick and may out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging upside down from trees. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their huge curved claws. ☐☐ Food regimen: Their weight loss program consists of termites, ants, and fruit. ☐☐ Dangerous? They are one of the aggressive bears, with the most attacks on humans, largely due to shock encounters. They blow the dust around with large puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 toes away. Sloth bears stand their ground if threatened and don't mix nicely with rhinos and elephants, typically charging at each other when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's final brief-fronted bear. The name "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that look like glasses. This susceptible species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. ☐☐ Dimension: They're mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to seventy nine inches tall. ☐☐ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last short-faced bear and the only bear native to South America. ☐☐ Features: The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that typically appear to be glasses. They spend most of their time in timber where they construct nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard precious fruit and carcasses. ☐☐ Food plan: Spectacled bears are largely herbivores with a food regimen consisting of largely cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they'll opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. ☐☐ Dangerous? Dwelling in distant mountains, these shy bears will be the least dangerous of all bear species. Their bodies are smaller than polar bears however larger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a rare hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in both nature and captivity. Grolar bear conduct is closer to the polar bear. They characteristic the long necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, similar to how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, but have not been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot but DNA checks had been unable to find out what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas are usually not bears, they are burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they're indestructible, microscopic animals that may survive in space. Most bear assaults happen when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Crimson pandas? They're in their very own family which can be closer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS. Look ahead to

bear scat and bear tracks that will point out a bear is close by, by which case you want to be further vigilant. Here are just a few ideas you need to use to prevent bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies protected.

2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you are right here so they do not unintentionally startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack.

3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you'll have great intentions, a bear is prone to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself.

3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Gadgets (AT CAMP).** If you see a bear, do not attempt to method or feed it. This consists of food, but also your toiletries, for instance. Whichever methodology you select, be sure that it is a minimum of 200 ft away out of your tent so you do not appeal to bears to your campsite.

4. **Keep CALM.** In case you meet a bear, do not run. Try to make your self look as huge as possible, waving your arms above your head. You too can extend a jacket above your head to make yourself look larger. Lock these things in a bear canister or use a bear bag to grasp them up in a tree. Do not scream or try to scare the bear.

5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A final RESORT).** Communicate to it calmly and slowly again away. Full instruction on how to use bear spray here. If the bear is dangerously close (30 toes) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming barely downward.

6. **Battle Again.** If all else fails and a bear assaults you, don't play dead. Which bear is the largest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 feet long, and 4.0 to 5.25 toes tall, the most important bear by both size and weight is the polar bear. The biggest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Combat again with all of your strength and hope that it will again down. Which bear is essentially the most dangerous? All bears are dangerous if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is known [giant koala teddy](#) for probably the most assaults. When in bear nation, it's at all times clever to carry bear spray. It's well deserved, particularly when cubs are round. Every year there are approximately forty six grizzly assaults, 6 leading to loss of life. In North America, grizzly bears have the most fearsome fame. Which bear is the strongest? While you're most likely to see an American black bear, on common there is only one attack per year. By way of raw chew energy, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chunk reigns supreme. All bears are strong and to not be messed with. When utilizing the chew drive quotient (chunk energy relative to dimension), the solar bear packs essentially the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found within the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the hearth but sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he became an icon and to today is the star of the longest-running public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear identified for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. More importantly Yogi Bear has inspired numerous via-hikers to try to grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging but receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He is an easygoing, friendly bear who lives a duty-free way of life. He also is likely to be the primary bear to obtain his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son typically would go to at the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada near where he was from. Chris additionally wrote The way to Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal components backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After via-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic ideas, guides and how-to's in your inbox every two weeks.

